

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Gschwend**FIRST NAME:** Achim**PROGRAM CODE:** MBASD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID need to ask for access)The author used the following software: Microsoft Word for Mac 2015, Zotero 5.0.88

AN INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

As a new EUCLID arrival and novice student of the Master of Business Administration in Sustainable Development (MBASD) program, I want to learn the craft of academic writing. Due to the functions of my professional carrier, I am a seasoned yet biased technical type of writer. Intrinsically motivated, I am used to adapting change. Therefore, I decided to let go and to discover the entire assigned material at a beginning glance. The journey begins, and my strategy was to review the material and to spontaneously note down questions. Unbiasedly absorbing the DNA of EUCLID's academic workflow guides me daily through studies. Many questions were organizational related to the EUCLID institution, its infrastructure and the MBA study program. Some questions addressed the general needs of time-management, study techniques and workflow. At that stage, I was still far away from any concrete concepts at all. Further attributes enriched the notes catalogue by referencing videos timestamps and PDF page numbers. Categorization supported the grouping of two main study objectives, standardization and workflow. I then could visually mind-map notes, having my central question on top-level: What does the lecturer want me to learn in this period one course? I recognised the need for terms definition before the classification of objectives. This led me to a tree diagram of subjects. Upon this visualization, I structured this Response Paper (RP), replaced questions by answers and findings, and filled the RPs body. This was exactly the concept that I required. With this RP, I aim to apply academic working techniques and the inherent iterative workflow of academic writing for the first time.

2) DEFINITIONS

As I am rather used to translate and define business requirements terms for a technical audience of software developers without any further room of interpretation, I begin with a classic breakdown of definitions. By this approach, I analysed what the three keywords of the course title being Academic, Writing and EUCLID mean to me, at my current state of novice innocence. This gave me the confidence required to discover the academic writing terrain.

a) Academic

Academic is for me both, a descriptive adjective and a noun. It practically stands as a surrogate for a skill-set to elaborate complex context in a traceable and structured way. It is seen as the art of creating smart flow in writing by using logical connectors and avoidance of contractions (EUCLID 2019, 12). The term academic encompasses strategic notes taking techniques, such as highlighting, commenting, collecting text passages for potential oral examination or quiz questions (EUCLID 2015, 03:56). Ethic aspects in Academics must be considered. Academic is about referencing to proof evidence of debated opinions. As a student and RP author, credible academic sources for support and evidence must be applied and essays obligatory contain references. Therefore, proper referencing avoids plagiarism, which is considered as a serious academic offence (EUCLID 2019, 5–6).

b) Writing

I understand Writing as a tool of academic expression, ranging from an intuitive medium of talented to a learnable craft for the ordinary. Writing is the activity to design the academic deliverables, as listed on the EUCLID ACA-401 checklist such as Essay, Thesis, Master Paper (MP) and this very RP. While analysing the coursepack, analogies to my experiences in both, house construction projects and songwriting practice came to my mind. Writing an essay is like planning a house build or composing songs. As Architects draft construction plans that are often revised due to unforeseen changing client requirements under communal infrastructure limitations. As musical composers drafting musical ideas and harmonic conclusion within the arrangement or orchestration, verses with storytelling lyrics, bridges to create tension in harmonies and clear wording for the chorus' core message. As an author, I likewise seek for a robust structure of having an introduction, followed by the controversial body content that should lead to a conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 1–4). My good old songwriter tricks matched: Keep distance for some days! Tweak, simplify and fine-tune the piece! Add an introduction at the very last just before finally recording the tune! And indeed, the rules of thumb for Writing Papers of Chapter 3 ultimately recalled me (EUCLID 2019, 14–16).

c) EUCLID

The supplementary video material presented, serves as a perfect introduction to EUCLID's technical workflow on both, the course management system (CMS) and the learning management system (LMS). The motivational video overview sharpened my dedication and sense for time management required to fulfil EUCLID's seven-periods cycle concept. EUCLID has a fundus of available resources and supplied material. I still need to request access to the online library and the Grammarly license for their MS Word plug-in. And I am sure that a non-native foreign English speaker like me can improve a lot by using tools like Grammarly. EUCLID is also the respected academic institution that imposes alignment to expected formalities and necessary rules of standardisation for both, communication between stakeholders and scope of the deliverables concerned (EUCLID 2015, 03:56).

3) OBJECTIVES

As the main desire of a lecturer is that students transfer know-how gathering into a traceable and understandable form, I try systematically to classify my noted comments, questions and findings by the potential core objectives of the course. Standardization and workflow are my main classification groups.

d) Standardization

Standardization is imperative for the organizational aspects at EUCLID. Standardization ranges from file names to different types of citation and bibliography, depending on the academic artefacts involved. However, there is also areas of personalized standardization, like for example the choice of language setting and the style choice (EUCLID 2017, 05:10).

Even though there is a discrepancy in the usage of uppercase and lowercase at the first name and last name of the file naming convention between the presented Vimeo video and the EUCLID Checklist for Academic Papers PDF file, I decided to use uppercase, as it makes sense in alignment to the Course Code and the Paper Code. I also realized that the RP versions that are stated with an R1 until Rn miss the letter P, but in the example outlined, it is stated as RP. I consider this as a typo and adhere to the convention RP including the period number concerned, hence RP1 (EUCLID 2020, 1).

An academic essay must contain references (EUCLID 2019, 4). I consider the referencing style at Euclid University as a standardization. The compact in-text citation is appropriate for shorter RPs as opposed to footnote referencing for longer MPs (EUCLID 2019, 6–12). As I calculated in a spreadsheet the number of RPs and MPs that I need to produce for the entire MBASD, each with the minimum number of referenced citations expected, I truly believe that the helpful tool Zotero will quickly become my second-best friend. Concerning online works, I missed advice on how to reference videos for the in-

text citation. After I reviewed other sources, I realized that there are rules for the longer bibliography reference only (Caulfield 2019). Finally, I proactively decided to note down the minutes and seconds of the video as a surrogate for pages of an online book.

Style standardization is expected for all artefacts, being it Turabian style for citation, as well as to use the text formats Euclid University expects that are available in the format ribbon of the artefacts templates (EUCLID 2017, 12:01).

A Crib sheet is something new to me, but I categorized it as well as a necessary standardization. EUCLID emphasizes on standards for the style used and rules for applicable abbreviations, forms of capitalization of text characters, compound words, italics and quotation marks, the spelling of numbers, as well as page and text formats (EUCLID 2019, 44–55). Especially with compound words, I recognised that students may deal with annoying deviating interpretations of grammar automation tools used, even if language settings are the same.

e) Workflow

In the beginning, there is always a blank piece of paper. This experience share students, authors, composers, artists, designers and architects likewise. While scrutinising the assigned study material, I was searching for Tips and best practice advice on the production process of academic writing. I was wondering which strategies to consider and which plannable and actual hands-on activities are expected by the practical craft of essay writing. An agile mindset for the iterative study working process is required, to enlighten the beginning's overwhelming chaos. As an old ironic Swabian saying of my grandmother tells with a blink of an eye: Those who tidy up a lot are only too lazy to search.

The coursepack confirmed me that academic writing in practice is everything but not a linear process. In contrary, it is based upon strict time management, active reading with note-taking, comments and questions gathering. A regular review, grouping, categorizing and structuring of findings into core bullet points is a potentially strong tactic towards drafting a classic structure having three the main parts, introduction, body and conclusion. Academic writing is an iterative process that encompasses regular breaks of revision and proofreading. I consider the tip to write the body before the introduction and conclusion as being a smart tactic (EUCLID 2019, 1–3). However, I found myself drafting the conclusion first as my home-base haven. Then I sketched with diagrams the raw structure I needed to outline in the introduction. The bullet points of the body were gradually enriched by material and references while sailing home to my conclusion.

Chapter 2 and 3 of the coursepack will serve as my reference book for papers to come. The explanation on types of quotations, citation, paraphrasing, single phrasing, bibliography referencing is more than standardization. It is best practice advice to avoid plagiarism and to work in a proper academic way (EUCLID 2019, 5–13).

The literature review sections in Chapter four of the coursepack provide practical tips on wording, advice concerning grammar rules, punctuation rules, as well as syntax tips

on subject and object switches (EUCLID 2019, 17–23). In a modern world of supportive digital tools, it remains at the writers' distinction to judge upon style and phrasing created by these algorithms. Even though it is time-consuming, but a human sense check of algorithmic results with the coursepack being the benchmark is very best practice for me.

Today's business communication in the banking industry is almost distorted beyond recognition by abbreviations. Latin jargon is often used in my mother tongue German. Hence, I appreciate the best practice advice of the coursepack on how to avoid jargon, when to apply Latin expressions, and I try to incorporate simple English into my future works to my best effort (EUCLID 2019, 56–61).

4) CONCLUSION

It is the power of words that can change lives and opinions, moves individuals and crowds, forms nations and influence the whole world. The course lesson sharpened my responsibility as a writer on how to use words in academic writing. This introductory course also helped me to better understand EUCLID as an organization. In terms of answering the RPs main question, what the lecturer wants me to learn in this period one course, I realized that both, the familiarization of standardization and the appliance of workflow best practice, impacted me most. My deeper analysis of study material assured me that this course offers more than enhancements in academic writing skills. It inspired me to re-think my learning approach. Modern helping tools, like Grammarly or Zotero, encouraged me to search for further devices and apps to enable and enhance my paperless workflow for online study. As the sustainable path is the goal thereby the course offers the toolkit necessary to constantly improve, to pave and to master it.

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